

TABLE 1—N'-(R-BENZOYL)-N''-(4-N-BENZYL-N-CYANOETHYLAMINO-2-METHYL BENZYLIDENE)-HYDRAZINE(IV)

No.	R	m.p. (°C)	Yield% from aldehyde	Yield% from I	Molecular Formula	Found	% N* Required
1.	H	168	88.1	74	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₄ O	13.79	14.14
2.	3-NO ₂	126	75.0	54	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₃	15.77	15.87
3.	4-NO ₂	202	83.3	68	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₃	15.56	15.87
4.	2-Cl	143	84.0	34	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₄ OCl	13.29	13.01
5.	4-Cl	164	59.9	72	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₄ OCl	12.83	13.01
6.	2-CH ₃	138	61.0	44	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O	13.52	13.66
7.	3-CH ₃	140	63.3	57	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O	13.95	13.66

* All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analysis.

N'-(Benzoyl)-N''-(4-N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl-benzylidene)-hydrazine(IV) :

Method-A :

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde (0.001 mol), was dissolved in 10 ml of boiling ethanol. Benzoic acid hydrazide (0.001 mol) was added to it in small portions with shaking. The reaction mixture was refluxed for two hours. The product thus separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Method-B :

Schiff's base (0.001 mol) and benzoic acid hydrazide (0.001 mol) were suspended in ethanol (10 ml) containing two drops of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for two hours, cooled and filtered. The product recrystallised from ethanol.

All the seven compounds listed in Table 1 were prepared by both the methods. Their i.r. spectra were perfectly superimposed.

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl-benzylidene diethylmalonate(V) :

Method-A :

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde (0.001 mol), diethylmalonate (0.001 mol) and four drops of piperidine were taken in a round bottomed flask and the mixture heated in an oil bath for 5 hours at 100-105°. The product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 124° (yield, 51.8%). (Found : C, 70.58 ; H, 6.92 ; N, 6.74%. C₂₅H₂₈N₂O₄ requires C, 71.43 ; H, 6.67 ; N, 6.67%).

Method-B :

Schiff's base (0.001 mol), diethylmalonate (0.001 mol) and four drops of piperidine were taken in a round bottomed flask and the mixture heated in an oil bath for 5 hours at 100-105°. The

product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 124° (yield, 38%).

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Synthesis of Chalcones from 2-Hydroxy-3-Bromo-4-*n*-Propoxy-5-Nitroacetophenone as Antibacterial Agents

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THE germicidal, bactericidal, fungicidal and carcinogenic action of chalcones and analogous compounds have been reported by various workers¹⁻¹¹. Wilson and coworkers¹² observed that methoxy and hydroxy chalcones can check up the destruction of adrenaline. The present investigation is an attempt to synthesise chalcones having bromo and nitro groups and to study their antibacterial activity against positive bacteria (*S.aureus*) and gram negative bacteria (*E.coli*).

The chalcones were prepared by condensing 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-*n*-propoxy-5-nitroacetophenone and aldehydes in presence of alkali following the method of Sorge^{1,2}. The chalcones were characterised by preparing their benzoyl derivatives, elemental analysis and uv and ir spectra. The elemental analysis for Br for synthesised chalcones were within $\pm 0.5\%$ of calculated value.

Bromination of these chalcones was studied using bromine in acetic acid when $\alpha : \beta$ dibromo-chalcones were obtained. The reactivity of the dibromides was examined with potassium iodide in acetone when the original chalcones were regenerated.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-4-n-propoxy-5-nitroacetophenone :

2-Hydroxy-4-*n*-propoxy-5-nitroacetophenone (16.0 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (80 ml). To this solution bromine in acetic acid (43 ml, 10%) was added with constant stirring. After keeping overnight at room temperature (25-30°), it was poured in water (400 ml), separated product was filtered, washed with water, dilute sodium bisulphite solution (5%) and water. It crystallised from ethanol as long pale yellow needles, m.p. 72°, yield 17.0 g.

Analysis : Found : Br - 25.3%
 $C_{11}H_{13}O_5NBr$ requires : Br - 25.1%

2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-propoxy-5'-nitrochalcones :

2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-4-*n*-propoxy-5-nitroacetophenone (3.18 g., 0.01 mole) and the aldehyde (0.011 mole) were dissolved in ethanol (50 ml), potassium hydroxide solution (40%, 40 ml) was added to the above solution with shaking. The mixture was left for 24 hrs at room temperature (25-30°). On dilution with ice water and acidification with dil. HCl (1:1), a solid separated out
 $\lambda_{max}^{ethanol}$ 260, 320 nm, IR : ν_{max}^{KBr} 1615-1667 cm^{-1} (C=O),
 1550-1610 cm^{-1} (C=C).

The chalcones and their melting point are given in Table 1.

Benzoyl derivative of chalcone :

The benzoyl derivative of chalcone was prepared by heating a mixture of chalcone, benzoyl chloride and a few drops of pyridine on a water bath for five hrs. The compounds and their m.p. are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Substituent	Chalcone m.p. °C	Benzoyl derivative m.p. °C	$\alpha : \beta$ Dibromo- derivative m.p. °C
Nil	110	116	135
4-methoxy	128	78	55
2-methoxy	130	75	85
3-methoxy-			
4-hydroxy	74	80	69
4-nitro	125	95	96
4-chloro	140	110	175
2,4-dichloro	207	110	135

2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-propoxy-5'-nitrochalcone
 $\alpha : \beta$ Dibromide :

A mixture of the chalcone (0.5 g) in 20 ml acetic acid and solution of bromine in acetic acid (5 ml, 10%) was kept overnight at room temperature and then it was poured in ice-water. The product separated was washed with dilute sodium thiosulphate and water. The compounds and their m.p. are given in Table 1.

Debromination of $\alpha : \beta$ Dibromo-chalcone :

A mixture of the above dibromide (0.2 g) and potassium iodide (0.2 g) in dry acetone (25 ml) was refluxed on water bath at 60-70° for 2-3 hrs. The solid separated after removal of acetone and pouring the contents in water was washed with sodium thiosulphate solution (5%) and crystallised from ethanol. The product was identified as the original chalcone by direct comparison.

Antibacterial activity :

The germicidal characteristics were studied by agar-cup method using peptone, beef extract agar-agar as solid nutrient broth media. The bacteria selected for the screening were *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The inhibition of growth was checked in a presterilised petridish after 24 hrs and results were recorded by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition. It was observed that the chalcones with chlorine or nitro substituent as well as without substituent in aldehyde part exhibit considerable activity.

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Allylation of 2, 4-dihydroxyphenylbenzylketone (I) gave 4-allyloxy derivative(II) which was condensed with diethyl carbonate to give 7-allyloxy-4-hydroxy-3-phenylcoumarin(III) which on methylation with dimethylsulphate gave 7-allyloxy-4-methoxy-3-phenylcoumarin(IV). (IV), on Claisen migration gave two products, one soluble in NaHCO₃ solution, 8-allyl-4-7-dihydroxy-3-phenylcoumarin(V) and the other soluble in sodium hydroxide solution, 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-phenylcoumarin(VI). The structure of (VI) was confirmed by NMR spectrum which showed two doublets at δ 6.85 and δ 7.60 for two protons at C-6 and C-5 respectively which confirmed that the allyl migration has taken place at C-8 and not at C-6. The Claisen migration of 7-hydroxycoumarins is regiospecifically taking place at position-8 and this has been observed earlier by Trivedi *et al*⁹ and Seshadri *et al*⁸. The products (V) and (VI) on cyclisation with conc. sulphuric acid gave 2, 3-dihydro-7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo (2, 3-h)benzopyran(VII). Demethylation of (VI) occurred during cyclisation. (VII) on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal gave 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(2, 3-h) benzopyran (VIII).

Synthesis of 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-2, 3-dihydro-5-oxo-5H-furo(2, 3-h)benzopyran(XV) and 2, 9-dimethyl-5-hydroxy-6-phenyl-7-oxo-7H-furo(3, 2-g)benzopyran(XXIII) were achieved by carrying out the above series of reactions on 2, 4-dihydroxy-4'-methoxyphenylbenzylketone(IX) and 2, 4-dihydroxy - 3 - methylphenylbenzylketone (XVI) respectively.

Studies in the Synthesis of Furocoumarins :
Part XXV*

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I R₁=R₂=R₃=H; II R₁=R₂=H, R₃=-CH₂CH=CH₂; IX R₁=R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃; X R₁=H; R₂=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₃=OCH₃; XVI R₁=CH₃; R₂=R₃=H and XVII R₁=CH₃; R₂=CH₂-CH=CH₂; R₃=H

4-HYDROXY-3-PHENYLCOUMARIN derivatives are found to occur in nature and belong to the groups of isoflavonoids¹. Robustic acid, robustin, scandenin and wedelolactone are few examples of this type. In our previous work, we have reported the synthesis of furocoumarins of angelicin and psoralene²⁻⁶ types, we report here the synthesis of 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo (2, 3-h) benzopyran(VIII), 7-hydroxy-2-methyl-6-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-2, 3-dihydro-5-oxo-5H-furo (2, 3-h)benzopyran(XV) and 2, 9-dimethyl-5-hydroxy-6-phenyl-7-oxo-7H-furo-(3, 2-g)benzopyran (XXIV).

III R₁=R₂=R₄=R₅=H; R₃=-CH₂CH=CH₂; IV R₁=R₂=R₃=H; R₄=-CH₂CH=CH₂; R₅=H; V R₁=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₂=R₃=R₄=R₅=H; VI R₁=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₂=R₃=R₄=H; R₅=CH₃; VII R₁=R₂=R₄=H; R₃=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₅=CH₃; VIII R₁=OCH₃; IX R₁=R₂=H; R₃=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₄=CH₃; R₅=OCH₃; X R₁=R₂=H; R₃=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₄=CH₃; R₅=OCH₃; XI R₁=R₂=R₄=H; R₃=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₅=OCH₃; XII R₁=R₂=H; R₃=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₄=R₅=H; XIII R₁=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₂=R₃=R₄=H; R₅=OCH₃; XIV R₁=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₂=R₃=H; R₄=CH₃; R₅=OCH₃; XV R₁=CH₃; R₂=R₃=R₄=R₅=H; XVI R₁=R₂=H; R₃=CH₂CH=CH₂; R₄=R₅=H; XVII R₁=CH₃; R₂=R₃=H; R₄=R₅=CH₂CH=CH₂; XVIII R₁=R₂=H; R₃=R₄=CH₃; R₅=H; XIX R₁=R₂=H; R₃=R₄=CH₃; R₅=H; XX R₁=CH₃; R₂=R₃=R₄=H; R₅=CH₂CH=CH₂; XXI R₁=R₂=CH₃; R₃=R₄=H; R₅=CH₂CH=CH₂

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